

Design of a Kelvin cell acoustic metamaterial

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Abstract

Advancements in 3D print technology now allow the printing of structured acoustic absorptive materials at appropriate microscopic scales and sample sizes. Optimisation of parameter sets associated with a Kelvin Cell structure have the potential to develop various metabehaviours in the associated acoustic responses. The repeatability of the fundamental cell unit also provide a route for the development of viable macro models to simulate built up structures based on detailed models of the individual cell units. This paper describes a process to model, print and test such a sample. Manufacturing restraints will initially guide the optimised design and introduce response uncertainties associated with surface finishes and critical geometric dimensions. A "micro to macro" model is developed using a full visco thermal acoustic model of a single cell to develop a frequency dependent cell transfer matrix. The transfer matrices for the repeated cells may then be combined until sufficient material depth is achieved and efficiently generate an absorptivity for the material layer. Two prints using different processes (digital light processing (DLP) and selective laser melting (SLM)) of nominally the same kelvin cell structure. For the metal print the model predicts the absorptivity well once an allowance is made for the surface roughness. The DLP has a smoother finish with a lower geometric fidelity however the DLP sample is still well modelled by the process.

1. Introduction

The capabilities of additive manufacturing technologies now allowed previously unmanufacturable structures to be produced in numerous materials

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and at small scales. While terminology and definitions around metamaterials are evolving the authors are using following definition from the EU H2020 funded AERIALIST project: A metamaterial is a human-made compound, a structured material engineered to achieve a response not available in nature and for which the model of an equivalent continuum can be defined. In this context a metabehaviour is the response which characterises the material as a metamaterial. Efficient, low computational costs design tools are required to enable the development of targeted noise control solutions using acoustic metamaterials. One potential route for the design of acoustic metamaterials are absorptive materials with repeated inner structures rather than foams or fibrous structures where the inner geometries are randomised by the solidification processes. Whereas homogenisation is the route to developing macroscopic acoustic property prediction for the the latter, the former can be modelled by building up a macro model from a detailed repeatable cell analysis. The design of periodic structures for benchmark materials useful for validation of numerical codes is also a topic of interest at present [1] [2]. Recent papers on optimal sound absorber design (and experimental testing) using these strategies include [3], ultra thin metasurfaces [4] and space coiling metamaterials [5] and [6, 7]. These papers demonstrate the potential for additive manufacturing to realise complex metamaterial designs however the influence of the manufacturing tolerances on the material performance still needs to be assessed [2]. The Kelvin cell structure reported upon in this paper requires state of the art additive manufacturing capabilities to realise the micro-structure and the details of the lattice are such that the computational costs of producing and slicing the files in preparation for printing are at the limits of what can be achieved with commercial software. A very recent paper [8] uses the periodicity potential of printed foams to build up an efficient homogenised macroscopic acoustic model from a detailed analysis of the individual cell dynamics. The cell acoustics were captured from a combination of numerical static flow and electro static analyses which mimic bulk experimental test processes as advanced in [9]. The efficiency introduced here through individual cell modelling is an essential step to eventual development of design processes. A similar overall approach using an individual cell modelling strategy has also been demonstrated in [10] where a full viscothermal cell model incorporating an efficient WCAWE frequency sweep [11] was reported on to inform an Low Reduced Frequency (LRF) macroscopic model [12]. In the present paper the overall modelling concept is similar except the Kelvin Cell structure is built from primary solid components. A full viscothermal cell WCAWE model is used to drive a macroscopic model based on transfer matrix approach similar to the approach reported

in, for example, [13], and the results are verified against experimental data where sensitivity to geometric uncertainties caused primarily by the printing approach at this scale can be assessed.

1.1. Background models

The lossy acoustics in a fine absorptive medium can be modelled by linearised viscothermal fluid mechanical models. These are governed by the equation system given for example in Nijhof *et al.* [14]. Assuming a Stokesian assumption the linearised equations, assuming Stokesian behaviour, can be written as

$$\rho_0(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) + j\omega\rho = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$j\omega\rho_0\mathbf{v} = -\nabla p + \mu(\nabla \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{3}\nabla\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \quad (2)$$

$$j\omega\rho_0 C_p T = \kappa\Delta T + j\omega p \quad (3)$$

$$p = R(\rho_0 T + \rho T_0) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{v}, p, \rho, T, \mu, R, \rho_0, T_0, \kappa$ and C_p are the acoustic harmonic velocity, pressure, density, temperature, dynamic viscosity, gas constant, static density, static temperature, thermal conductivity, and specific heat at constant pressure. A finite element model implementing the above can be constructed using a mixed weak formulation following [14] and Zienkiewicz *et al.* [15] which can present the system in the matrix form

$$[\mathbf{K} + j\omega\mathbf{M}]\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{F} \quad (5)$$

As the density variable may be eliminated using the equation of state, Equation 4, each node will have five degrees of freedom including three velocity components, temperature and pressure stored in \mathbf{a} . The forcing vector \mathbf{F} then models boundary pressure loads, material injection and heat flux. \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{M} were constructed following the procedures for mixed formulations outlined in [15]. In order to develop a stable mixed model it is critical to use shape functions of one order less for the pressure and its related weighting functions, In this work quadratic 10 noded tetrahedral elements were used with linear functions for pressure and quadratic functions for the velocity and temperature. The redundant mid-side nodal pressure degrees of freedom were decoupled from the formulation and 2nd order volumetric and spatial integrations were used.

The general equation system in Section 1.1 has also shown itself to be amenable over the frequency ranges of interest to efficient Padé type

frequency sweeps such as the WCAWE method proposed by Slone *et al.* [11]. In the cell system modelled in this work, it the equation system required full solution only at a single centre frequency. The rest of the frequency range of interest was generated by WCAWE extrapolation based on derivatives up to order 12. The cell model with adequate mesh density to model the boundary layers which generated of the order of 12,000 nodes was thus easily solvable on a standard laptop computer.

1.2. From micro to macro:visco-thermal model to Transfer Matrix

Despite the efficiencies introduced by the individual cell modelling considerations above, solution of the full system equations is extremely expensive and is effectively impractical for any optimisation studies of built up systems of multiple conjoined cells. Clearly a model reduction strategy leading to a macro model is required.

A transfer matrix approach provides a key to building up full depth absorbent models from individual modelled test data. If the cell is considered a two port network using averaged pressure $\bar{p}(\omega)$ and velocity $\bar{u}(\omega)$ as the (frequency dependent) interface data, then we can write

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{p}_{inlet} \\ \bar{u}_{inlet} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{p}_{outlet} \\ \bar{u}_{outlet} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{T}(\omega)$ is the cell transfer matrix. The individual elements of the matrix can be determined by for example driving the system at inlet (a plane wave forcing was used in the present case) and then imposing an open ($p_{outlet} = 0$) followed by a closed boundary condition ($u_{outlet} = 0$). The open cell simulation then delivers

$$T_{12} = p_{inlet}/u_{outlet}; T_{22} = u_{inlet}/u_{outlet}; \quad (7)$$

whereas the closed cell simulation yields

$$T_{11} = p_{inlet}/p_{outlet}; T_{21} = u_{inlet}/p_{outlet}; \quad (8)$$

The overall multicell system response matrix $\mathbf{T}_{sys}(\omega)$ for n cells can then be quickly calculated from

$$\mathbf{T}_{sys} = \mathbf{T}^n \quad (9)$$

from which the surface impedance for a system with a closed backing can be determined using

Figure 1: The unit Kelvin Cell design defined within a cubic tessellation

$$Z = \frac{T_{sys11}}{\phi T_{sys21}} \quad (10)$$

where ϕ is the surface porosity. This can be estimated directly from the geometric model ($\phi=0.571$ for the present case). Alternatively the porosity could be set to one and transfer matrix prefixed to the system calculation to model the inlet manifold in detail. Other backing conditions can be also readily calculated using other combinations of the system transfer matrix entities. Finally the full depth absorptivity α can be assessed using

$$R = \frac{Z - \rho_0 c}{Z + \rho_0 c} \quad (11)$$

$$\alpha = 1 - |R|^2 \quad (12)$$

where c is the external sonic speed.

2. Visco-Thermal Kelvin Cell Model

In this study an absorptive layer 20 cells deep was considered with the cell form shown in figure 1.

The nominal lengths of the individual struts shown are $375 \mu\text{m}$ with diameters $400 \mu\text{m}$. A one eighth model of the complementary acoustic cavity

was geometrically modelled and meshed using gmsh 4.1.5 [16]. This had an open or closed outlet with a forced pressure inlet and a symmetry condition applied to the side walls. No slip and zero acoustic temperature conditions were applied to the curved wetted surface areas. Sample results for the temperature and axial velocity (open end condition) are shown in figures 2 (a) and (b) for the system running at 1000 Hz.

(a) Acoustic Temperature

(b) Axial Velocity

Figure 2: Example cell simulations - Open exit boundary conditions'

Note that in addition to the high number of degrees of freedom required per node (5) there is also a further requirement to locally refine the meshes within the boundary layers particularly as the frequencies rise. The indicative meshes shown here (12028 nodes) gave converged results. A further feature to note on the plots is the small aperture in the cell which generate significant local activity. In some of the manufactured models this tends to close. Simulations with it closed can be conveniently performed by simply placing a wall boundary conditions at that section of the inlet produced minor effects on averaged inlet and outlet data. For transfer matrix calculations we elected to close the apertures.

3. Multi-Cell Macro model

The next stage is then to model the full 20 cell structure using the efficient Helmholtz model using the transfer matrix approach described above. Although nominally set at 400 μm the cell models were rerun with appropriate strut diameters for the various materials. Space averaged pressure and normal velocity data were gathered with estimate of the porosity at the inlet. Once the cell transfer matrix was estimated the system matrix was formed by raising it to a power of 40 which could then modelled a hard-backed structure 30 mm deep. The entire laptop computation takes approximately 30 s. Simulation results are presented against experimental data in the two cases under study at the end of section 4.

4. Experimental Measurements

The relevant ISO standard for the measurement of the acoustical properties of the material is ISO 10534-2:2001. This standard describes the test rig and procedures for estimating the complex acoustic impedance of a material under normal incidence using the "two-microphone" or "transfer function" method. This methodology was used to calculate the reflection and absorption coefficients which are the usual measures used to quantify the performance of an acoustic material.

In order to facilitate impedance tube testing samples were manufactured using additive techniques. Due to the high resolution and precision required for the Kelvin cell material there are limited options available for additive manufacture of the samples. Selective laser melting (SLM) [17] and digital light processing (DLP) [18, 19] were chosen for manufacture of the samples. The SLM samples were manufactured with the 3D Systems Prox DMP 200

and in this work was used to manufacture in cobalt chrome. The machine has the following capabilities:

- Resolution: $x=100 \mu\text{m}$; $y=100 \mu\text{m}$; $z=20 \mu\text{m}$
- Material: metals - Titanium, CoCr, Aluminium, SS
- Build Volume: $x=140 \text{ mm}$; $y=140 \text{ mm}$; $z=125 \text{ mm}$
- Wall Thickness: $150 \mu\text{m}$
- Surface Roughness: Up to $5 \text{ Ra } \mu\text{m}$

The DLP samples were manufactured with an Anycubic Photon. The DLP process utilises a photomonomer reacting to light in a polymerisation reaction which results in a high level of crosslinking thus generating a solid object. The DLP process uses a LCD screen with a UV lamp, the LCD screen is used to illuminate and cure an entire layer with UV light. The machine has the following capabilities:

- Resolution: $x=47 \mu\text{m}$; $y=47 \mu\text{m}$; $z=25-100 \mu\text{m}$
- Material: polymer
- Build Volume: $x=115\text{mm}$; $y=65 \text{ mm}$; $z=155 \text{ mm}$

For both technologies entrained material must be removed which requires a combination of ultrasonic and compressed air cleaning. This process of cleaning limited the number of layers of Kelvin cells that could be manufactured at this scale to ten cells deep.

In normal incidence impedance tube tests the sample is backed by a hard, reflective termination. The custom rig used for this work is also shown in figure 3. In the experimental rig, the hard termination is provided by a 20mm thick piece of aluminium which can be bolted on the end of the tube.

The cut-on frequency for this tube means that it is only possible to perform tests reliably up to 3800 Hz. The lower limit is determined by the speaker and is in the region of 500Hz. On the left hand side of figure 3 we can see the BMS 4591 speaker which is driven by the output signal of a National Instruments DAQ which has been amplified by a power amplifier. The speaker bolts on to the end of the tube to provide a tight seal with little leakage of sound. The square section on the right of figure 3 is the sample holder which opens to hold cylindrical samples of 40mm diameter and up to 50mm thick.

GRAS 40PH array microphones were chosen to instrument the rig as they have a frequency response of ± 1 dB within 50 - 5,000 Hz and upper limit of the dynamic range of 135dB re 20 μPa allowing for testing up to high pressure amplitudes. The microphones are connected to the National Instruments DAQ and the signals are recorded in Matlab. The microphones are calibrated using the switching methods described in the standards to achieve a calibration transfer function which corrects for any differences in the behaviour of the microphones.

The impedance tube requires samples of a 40 mm diameter but due to the periodic structure of the Kelvin cell material a disk of this material will include many partial cells at the edges. These partial cells are impossible to manufacture due to unsupported overhangs in the print. To avoid these overhangs the entire sample was printed within a hard wall supporting ring. This hard wall ring was designed to have an inner diameter of 40 mm so as to allow an exact flush fit with the walls of the impedance tube. Custom sample holders were designed to enable this flush fit with the walls of the tube.

Figure 4 (a) shows the STL file of the sample. This file consists of a mesh with 8,825,219 vertices with a file size of 875 MB which is approaching the limit of what can be achieved on a standard desktop PC and processed by the printer's slicing software. The unit cell design is specified in the commercial nTopology Element software and then this software is used to generate the lattice of cells within the specified sample volume. The unit cell is specified within a cubic tessellation of 1.5 mm and with strut diameters of 0.4 mm. The samples and holder are shown in figure 5. Each disk consists of ten layers of 1.5 mm cells for a total depth of 15 mm and for the tests two disks were stacked in the sample holder to give a total depth of twenty layers.

The produced samples were then inspected using a Leica S6E stereomicroscope under 127X magnification. Images were captured and dimensioned with a dino-eye eyepiece camera and associated software. Figure 6 reports the locations where the three dimensions were taken from each microscopy image. Thirty two images were taken for each print process at various locations in the samples to give a total of ninety six measured values for each print process. The average dimensions are given in table 1. The SLM process produces a dimension for the struts which is 95% of that specified within the STL file. The DLP process produces a dimension for the struts which is 118% of that specified within the STL file. The extra width within the DLP print process may be due to lateral curing within the vat as the UV light disperses within the resin.

Figure 7 shows the results for the SLM (a) and DLP (b) samples. As can be seen from the images there is greater variability in the strut diameters than in the original STL file and the printers are not capable of regularly producing the smallest hole in the Kelvin cell lattice. The SLM print process includes some of these small holes but the DLP print processes entirely seals this feature due to entrained resin which subsequently cures.

The surface roughness is also visible particularly in the SLM sample on account of the particle driven process. In the DLP sample the LCD screen pixel size will also generate roughness through a voxel effect. From these observations the working effective strut diameter for the numerical model was assessed to be 0.4 mm as incorporated into the models presented earlier.

Figure 3: Impedance tube rig designed in compliance with ISO 10535-2

(a) CAD of impedance tube sample

(b) View of lattice structure

Figure 4: Computer aided design images

Figure 5: (a) Sample attached to build plate manufactured with a 3D Systems Prox DMP 200 (b) SLM and DLP sample disks (c) SLM sample in holder for impedance tube testing

Figure 6: Dimensioned locations in the lattice

	Average (mm)	Standard Error (mm)	Porosity ¹
SLM	0.381	0.016	0.606
DLP	0.474	0.020	0.515

Table 1: Mean strut dimensions and standard error for SLM and DLP printed samples.

(a) Microscopy image of the SLM produced sample

(b) Microscopy image of the DLP produced sample

Figure 7: Test sample images

To ensure repeatability of the testing and to investigate the impact of the manufacturing imperfections on the measurements each material was tested three times. During tests disks were mounted and dismounted between tests in order to be stacked in both front/back combinations. Figure 8 reports the mean and standard deviation of the absorption coefficient, α , for both the DLP (a) and SLM (b) samples. As can be seen from figure 8 both print processes provided a very precise result with negligible deviations between tests. It is likely that the partially sealed openings and the differing strut diameters are responsible for the different frequency behaviour between the two manufactured samples. The peak in the average α values of the DLP samples is below that of the SLM samples, perhaps as a result of the smoother surface finish in these samples.

Figure 8: Mean and Standard deviation of the absorption coefficient α (a) DLP samples (b) SLM samples

A comparison of the experimental and numerical results for both samples with modelled using the geometries summarised in table 1 are presented in figure 9. Although the numerical predictions underestimate the loss, they are positioned well on the frequency axis and show the expected mild sub-wavelength behaviour with a similar sensitivity to the mean geometric deviations between the two experimental samples. In both cases there is a tendency of the samples to develop struts which slightly neck. Relatively speaking this may generate greater error in the numerical model for the SLM sample which uses narrower mean strut diameters. As no account was taken of surface effects, which are clearly evident in the microscopy images in figure 7, tentative predictions are also included with a doubled viscosity which give very encouraging results.

Figure 9: Experimental vs numerical estimates for absorption coefficient

5. Discussion

The scale of the Kelvin cell material design presented here clearly pushes current additive manufacturing technologies to their limit in terms of resolution and precision. The experimental acoustic testing reveals the difference in print quality and precision between a state of the art SLM machine and the low cost desktop DLP machine. However there is promising agreement between the experimental measurement and the efficient micro-macro numerical simulation procedure. Notwithstanding experimental error, clear uncertainties in the modelling process also include those associated with dimensional estimates of narrower sections and the modelling of surface finish which is the clear differentiator of loss estimates associated with the granular SLM sample over the "voxelated" DLP sample.

6. Conclusions

The proposed structures were realised using state of the art additive manufacturing technologies and when used at the scale presented here, have highlighted the acoustic sensitivity to geometric and surface finish uncertainty.

The use of efficient viscothermal models at a cell level provides a direct route via the transfer matrix approach to modelling built up cellular acoustically absorptive structures.

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